

A Weather adjacency

We want to order the rows and columns of the weather adjacency matrices to reflect the geographical proximity of the stations. Specifically, stations that are geographically close should have their corresponding blocks of rows and columns placed next to each other as closely as possible. However, since the stations are located in a 2D space (longitude and latitude), they cannot be perfectly ordered in a single 1D sequence.

Instead, we use the Fiedler vector [1] to sort the matrix, as it provides a good approximation. The Fiedler vector is the eigenvector corresponding to the second smallest non-zero eigenvalue of a graph's Laplacian matrix. For T objects with a pair-wise $T \times T$ similarity matrix, the Fiedler vector is thus a T dimensional vector, associating a scalar value to each of the T entities. The entities can then be sorted in the order of the magnitudes of their corresponding scalar values.

We build a distance matrix from the stations' geographical coordinates to get a degree of similarity, transform this matrix to the graph Laplacian form, and compute its Fiedler vector, with the resulting sort order visualized in Figure 2.

The adjacencies sorted according to the Fiedler vector are shown in Figure 1, where it is clear that only the proposed model's adjacency shows diagonal structure. Note that the single diagonal line for MTGNN corresponds to a zeroed main diagonal. This complements the results reported in the main paper. It matches the presentation used for the other data sets, whereas for this data we used the more illustrative spatial plots in the main paper.

Figure 1. The adjacency matrices from each model for the US Weather dataset. Only the proposed method shows a clear diagonal structure (outside the zeros on the main diagonal) when the adjacencies are sorted geographically. The adjacencies are sorted according to the Fiedler vector.

Figure 2. Fiedler sort order of the 152 weather stations

B Eigengaps

In Table 2 of the main paper we reported for each method two alternative numbers of clusters. The choices corresponded to the two largest eigengaps of the graph Laplacians of the adjacency matrices (plus one). To confirm these numbers, we show in Figure 3 the full set of eigengaps.

Figure 3. The gaps between consecutive eigenvalues of the graph laplacian built from each model type's adjacency matrix

References

- [1] M. Fiedler. Algebraic connectivity of graphs. *Czechoslovak mathematical journal*, 23(2):298–305, 1973.